

UV Spectral Characteristics of 2-and 3-Alkyl, Arylalkyl and Aryl Substituted 4-Ketoquinazolines

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Received August 17, 1968 Revised MSS received July 7, 1971

UV spectra of 2-Me, -Et, -CH₂Ph, -(CH₂)₂ Ph, -Ph, *o*- and *p*-NO₂Ph, *o*- and *p*-OMePh, -*o*-ClPh and their 3-(H), methyl and phenyl substituted-4-ketoquinazoline derivatives have been studied in ethanol solutions.

A systematic study of the Niementowski 4-ketoquinazoline synthesis and 2(R)-3 : 1 : 4 benzoxazone-amine reaction undertaken by Patel and coworkers^{1,2}, furnished a variety of 2(R)-3(R')-4-ketoquinazoline derivatives. Ultraviolet spectra of these compounds have been studied for their general characterisation and for investigating the spectra-structure relationship. UV spectra of simple and 2-methyl and 2-phenyl-3-(H and Me)-4-ketoquinazolines have been studied by various workers^{3,4}.

The UV spectra of the 4-ketoquinazoline derivatives listed in tables 1 to 3 have been studied in ethanol solution. The spectrum of a 4-ketoquinazoline normally comprises three bands, typical of a bicyclic aromatic system⁵. They are designated in the order of increasing wavelength as β , para and α bands following the nomenclature proposed by Clar⁵.

2-Alkyl and 2-arylalkyl-3-(H)-4-ketoquinazolines : Examination of the ultraviolet spectral data given in the table 1 reveals that the spectra of the 2-alkyl and 2-arylalkyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines are closely related with regard to the nature, number, position and extent of absorption and the fine structure of the constituent bands. The α band exhibits a fine structure of two sub-bands in each case. As expected due to the intervening methylene group (or groups)-2-benzyl and 2- β -phenylethyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines² exhibit almost same spectra as the 2-alkyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines.

2-Aryl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines : The spectra of 2-phenyl⁴, 2-*p*-anisyl⁶, 2-*p*-nitrophenyl⁷-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines (Table 2, R' = H) would differ markedly from those of

the 2-alkyl and 2-arylalkyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines (Table-1) because of the possible resonance interaction of the following type between the 2-aryl group and the π electron system of the

quinazoline moiety the relative importance of the charged structures II and III would depend upon the nature of the group R. Their spectra comprise only two bands which seem to correspond to the β band and para bands. The β band, which is usually in the form of an inflection, a shoulder or a general absorption, appears at a longer wavelength than the corresponding band in the spectrum of 2-alkyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline. The para band in the spectrum of these 2-aryl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines is a broad band of high intensity and had undergone such a rapid bathochromic shift as to swamp the low intensity α band.

TABLE I
Spectral data of 2(R)-3(R')-4-ketoquinazolines

R	R'	β -band		para-band		α -band	
		$m\mu$	$\log \epsilon$	$m\mu$	$\log \epsilon$	$m\mu$	$\log \epsilon$
H	H	225	4.34	265	3.66	301	3.48
						315(s)	3.31
Me	H	225	4.43	264	3.84	304	3.61
						315(s)	3.52
Me	Me	225	4.45	266	3.91	305	3.61
						315(s)	3.51
Me	Ph	225	4.56	266	3.99	305	3.61
						315(s)	3.51
Et	H	225	4.45	264	3.88	304	3.64
						315(s)	3.53
Pr	H	225	4.37	264	3.84	304	3.58
						315(s)	3.49
CH ₂ .Ph	H	226	4.50	266	3.95	306	3.67
						315(s)	3.57
(CH ₂) ₂ .Ph	H	226	4.44	265	3.94	305	3.70
						315(s)	3.57

s = Shoulder.

As compared to the positions of the corresponding bands in the spectrum of 2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline⁴, the β and para bands in the spectrum of 2-(*p*-nitro) phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline appear at longer wavelengths, as expected, due to the presence of the nitro group in the para position. However, the spectrum of 2-*o*-nitrophenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline⁶ is a three band spectrum and the bands appear at shorter wavelengths than the corresponding bands in the spectrum of its 2-phenyl analogue. A molecular model constructed for this compound using Courtauld Atomic Models indicated that due to the presence of the *o*-nitro group, the 2-*o*-nitrophenyl group cannot be accommodated in a strain-free planar configuration in the plane of the main quinazolone moiety resulting in the steric inhibition of resonance between these two moieties⁸ which causes the relative hypsochromic shift.

TABLE 2

Spectral data of 2(Ar)-3(R')-4-ketoquinazolines.

Ar	R'	β -band		para-band		α -band	
		m μ	log ϵ	m μ	log ϵ	m μ	log ϵ
Ph	H	238	4.49	289	4.19		
Ph	Me	230	4.44	280	4.09		
Ph	Ph	230	4.50	276	4.13		
(<i>p</i>)NO ₂ .Ph	H	251(s)	4.15	315	4.05		
(<i>p</i>)NO ₂ .Ph	Me	251(s)	4.17	305*	4.03		
			much less				
(<i>p</i>)NO ₂ .Ph	Ph	251	distinct shoulder	292*	4.13		
(<i>o</i>)NO ₂ .Ph	H	224	4.51	263	4.07	305	3.88
						315(s)	3.80
(<i>p</i>)OMe.Ph	H	240 to 260	**	300	4.34		
(<i>p</i>)OMe.Ph	Me	277	4.27	≈304(s)	4.05		
(<i>p</i>)OMe.Ph	Ph	275	4.42	≈304(s)	4.14		
(<i>o</i>)OMe.Ph	H	240(s)	4.29	305	4.15		
(<i>o</i>)Cl.Ph	H	266	4.44	276	4.01	315(s)	3.66

* Broad band with no distinct maximum and with tail part undergoing a rapid hypochromic effect from 310 m μ onwards.

** General absorption.

The β band in the spectrum of the 2-*p*-anisyl compound has smoothed out and shows a general absorption in the region from 240 to 260 m μ while, its para band is a broad band with λ_{\max} near about 300 m μ and is more intense than the corresponding band in the spectrum of 2-phenyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline. This trend in the spectrum of the 2-*p*-anisyl compound seems to be due to the direct resonance-interaction of the type shown in structure II (R = OMe).

In the case of the 2-*o*-anisyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline²⁶, the possible steric effect exerted by the *o*-methoxy group would not allow the main ketoquinazoline nucleus and the *o*-anisyl ring to be coplanar. This might be the reason why its β band is less intense than the corresponding band of its 2-phenyl analogue, although the para band intensity is similar. However, both bands of the former appear at longer wavelengths than those of the latter. Braude and Forbes⁹ have also observed a similar type of red shift in case of *o*-substituted diphenyls.

TABLE 3

Spectral data of 2(R)-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines

R	Medium	pH	β -band		para-band		α -band		
			m μ	log ϵ	m μ	log ϵ	m μ	log ϵ	
H	*Neutral	8.60	225	4.34	265	3.66	301	3.48	
							315(s)	3.31	
	Acidic	1.20	232	4.40	271	3.81	295	3.64	
306(s)							3.69		
Me	*Neutral	8.10	225	4.43	264	3.84	304	3.61	
							315(s)	3.52	
	Acidic	1.50	233	4.41	270	3.78	295	3.60	
304(s)							3.53		
Et	*Neutral	8.78	225	4.45	264	3.88	304	3.64	
							315(s)	3.53	
	Acidic	1.20	233	4.41	271	3.82	295	3.64	
304(s)							3.56		
CH ₂ .Ph	*Neutral	8.60	226	4.50	266	3.95	306	3.67	
							315(s)	3.57	
	Acidic	1.30	232	4.42	271	3.91	295	3.71	Inflexion
306							3.56	"	
(CH ₂) ₂ .Ph	*Neutral	8.90	226	4.44	265	3.94	305	3.70	
							315(s)	3.57	
	Acidic	1.30	232	4.38	271	3.86	295	3.59	Inflexion
305							3.46	"	
Ph	*Neutral	8.20	238	4.49	289	4.19			
	Acidic	1.57	237	4.36	291	4.17			
	Basic	11.60	249	4.50	308	4.06			

* In the sense that H⁺ or OH⁻ solutions have not been added to 80% ethanolic solution.

2-Substituted-3(H)-4-ketoquinazoline at different pHs : The ultraviolet spectra of some potentially tautomeric 2- and/or 4-hydroxy pyridine, pyrimidine, quinoline, quinazoline, have been studied by various workers¹⁰. They resemble those of the corresponding N-methyl derivative having fixed amide structure and differ from those of the corresponding *o*-methyl derivatives in alcohol or aqueous solution indicating that these compounds exist almost predominantly in the amide-form¹⁰.

The ultraviolet spectra of the compounds reported in the table 3 have been studied at three different *pH*'s. The spectra of simple³, 2-methyl¹¹, 2-ethyl, 2-benzyl, and 2-(β -phenyl) ethyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines resemble each other very closely in their neutral, acidic and basic media respectively.

In the basic medium only the para band has undergone somewhat appreciable bathochromic shift while, the corresponding shift of the α band is not much. In a truly phenolic compound both these bands would undergo a very rapid bathochromic shift in the basic medium¹². The shift in the acid medium is also not significant suggesting that these compounds exist almost mainly in the amide form and the contribution of the enolic form is insignificant¹².

2(R)-3(R')-4-ketoquinazolines : A close similarity of the spectral data of 2-phenyl, 2-*p*-nitrophenyl and 2-*p*-anisyl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines respectively with their corresponding 3-methyl and 3-phenyl derivatives (Table 2) indicate that these 2-aryl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines also exist almost mainly in the amide-form. The observed hypochromic shift of the para band of the 2-aryl-3-substituted-4-ketoquinazoline relative to that of the corresponding band in the spectrum of the 2-aryl-3(H)-4-ketoquinazolines may be ascribed to the steric inhibition of resonance in the 3-substituted compounds. An examination of the molecular model using Courtauld Atomic Models reveals that it is not possible for 3-methyl or 3-phenyl group and 2-phenyl group to remain in the plane of the main quinazoline ring system.

EXPERIMENTAL

The 4-ketoquinazolines derivatives whose spectra have been studied were purified by two recrystallisations and dried by keeping the powdered sample in a vacuum desiccator over calcium chloride for 24 hrs.

The UV spectra were determined on a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer using silica absorption cells of thickness of 1.000 ± 0.012 cm. In the study of UV spectra at different *pH*'s, the solvent composition was maintained constant. The basic, neutral or acidic solution was prepared by mixing 80 ml of the ethanolic stock solution of the given sample with 20 ml of 1.0*M* OH⁻, distilled water or 1.0*M* H⁺ solution respectively.

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